

SafeMut simulation (WES)

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth
- Real variant
- Simulated variant

Batch

- A 1
- B 2
- C 3
- D 4
- E 5
- F 6

updep(0)160i

Allele fraction (AF)

Mutation

c.597A>T 1

c.1127C>T 2

c.439C>T 2

.CNT

SafeMut simulation (WES)

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth
- Real variant
- Simulated variant

Batch

- A: 1
- B: 2
- C: 3
- D: 4
- E: 5
- F: 6

Allele fraction (AF)

.CNT

SafeMut simulation (WES)

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth
- Real variant
- Simulated variant

Batch

- A 1
- B 2
- C 3
- D 4
- E 5
- F 6

SafeMut simulation (WES)

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth (black circle)
- Real variant (red circle)
- Simulated variant (green circle)

Batch

- A 1
- B 2
- C 3
- D 4
- E 5
- F 6

Allele fraction (AF)

(update)1000

Mutation

c.4286G>C

c.1127C>T

c.3742G>A

c.8626C>T

c.811A>G

c.3057G>C

c.81G>C

c.4065C>T

c.5624C>T

1CNT

SafeMut simulation (WES)

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth (black circle)
- Real variant (red circle)
- Simulated variant (green circle)

Batch

- A (1)
- B (2)
- C (3)
- D (4)
- E (5)
- F (6)

Allele fraction (AF)

log10(depth)

Mutation

.CNT

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